

Current-driven dynamics of chirality in quasi-one-dimensional easy-plane helimagnets with high anisotropy

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 (Dated: March 17, 2026)

Control of chirality in helimagnets can be achieved by applying an electric current and a magnetic field during the phase transition process, as well as by means of a domain wall motion. In a continuum theory of a frustrated magnet, we show the possibility of driven dynamics of a chiral (Hubert) wall, connecting the domains with opposite chiralities, with the help of the non-adiabatic effect of the spin-transfer torque. In addition, we find another force, which acts on the magnetization profile, induced along the chiral wall by current, in the presence of a magnetic field. The conditions of the chirality switching due to the asymmetry of the magnetic potential energy in the presence of field and current are derived.

I. INTRODUCTION

A broad class of multiferroics is represented by the so-called frustrated magnetic systems in which the magnetization (or Néel vector) forms a helical periodic structure intermediate between ferromagnets and antiferromagnets [1].

Schemes for controlling the helimagnetic structure using a magnetic field with a change in magnetotransport properties due to the formation of a magnetic kink crystal [2] and discrete helicoidal states [3] have been demonstrated. However, the dynamics of domain walls driven by spin currents in these materials remain largely unexplored; the translational motion of domain walls in helimagnets may be accompanied by the formation of magnetization “vortices” [4].

Recent experiments show the possibility of chirality switching in conducting helimagnets by crossing the phase transition point with the application of electric current in the field-decreasing process [5], as well as near the paramagnetic state, assisted by the temperature [6]. It was shown in micromagnetic simulations [7], that the controllability of the switching process significantly depends on the value of magnetic anisotropy. To our knowledge, the theory of dynamics of magnetic moments in helimagnets under the action of an electric current and a magnetic field has not been proposed yet. The main goal of this paper is to build such a description within a continuum approximation.

In this work, we theoretically investigate the motion of chiral domain walls under the action of an electric current in a quasi-one-dimensional centrosymmetric helimagnet, which has a doubly degenerate ground state – right- or left-handed helicoid. Using a continuum approach, we demonstrate the possibility of translational motion of the chiral domain wall by the non-adiabatic effect of an electric current, while the adiabatic contribution leads to the renormalization of an equilibrium helical angle, which causes the formation of domain walls along the sample. The simultaneous application of field and current gives an additional contribution to the domain wall velocity, which can be captured via the collective coordinates method. The possibility of chirality switching by the effects of field and current is estimated in the easy-plane approximation by analyzing the modification of potential energy of a helimagnet.

II. MODEL: EFFECTIVE CONTINUUM LAGRANGIAN

To construct a continuous theory of the dynamics of magnetic moments in a helimagnet, we start from the Heisenberg model of a 1D spin chain, considering ferromagnetic ($J > 0$) interaction between nearest neighbors, antiferromagnetic ($J' < 0$) next-nearest-neighbor exchange, and strong easy-plane anisotropy $K > 0$:

$$H = \sum_i \left\{ -J \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+1} - J' \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i+2} + K (\mathbf{S}_i \cdot \hat{x})^2 \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{S}_i = S \cdot \mathbf{n}_i$, S is the spin of magnetic atoms and \mathbf{n}_i is a unit vector along the direction of a spin, $|\mathbf{n}_i| = 1$. \hat{x} is the hard axis, so that the helical rotation occurs in the (yz)-easy plane. By assuming small gradients, one can treat \mathbf{n}_i as a smooth field $\mathbf{n}(x)$ and perform a Taylor expansion up to the fourth term $\partial_x^4 \mathbf{n}$. Now going from the summation to the integration along \hat{x} , we rewrite the Hamiltonian [8]:

$$H = N_{\perp} S^2 \int \frac{dx}{a} \left\{ \frac{a^2}{2} (\partial_x \mathbf{n})^2 [J + 4J'] - \frac{a^4}{24} (\partial_x^2 \mathbf{n})^2 [J + 16J'] + K n_x^2 \right\}. \quad (2)$$

with a being the lattice constant and $N_{\perp} = S_{\perp}/a^2$ is the cross-sectional area in units of a^2 (we set this factor equal to 1 for simplicity, as it does not affect the dynamics of the system). It is convenient to introduce the helical angle $\tilde{\theta} = \arccos(-J/4J')$ between neighboring spins, where the condition $J' < -J/4$ holds below the helimagnetic transition temperature. For the continuous approximation to be valid, we assume $\tilde{\theta} \ll 1$ and write the energy in terms of J and $\tilde{\theta}$ by expanding $\cos \tilde{\theta} \approx 1 - \tilde{\theta}^2/2$ similarly to [1]:

$$H = S^2 \int \frac{dx}{a} \left\{ \frac{Ja^2}{2} \left[-\frac{\tilde{\theta}^2}{2} (\partial_x \mathbf{n})^2 + \frac{a^2}{4} (\partial_x^2 \mathbf{n})^2 \right] + K n_x^2 \right\}. \quad (3)$$

FIG. 1. Depiction of a chiral (Hubert) domain wall (in the middle) connecting left-handed (on the left) and right-handed (on the right) domains. Spins rotate around \hat{x} -axis, the rotation stops at the center of a DW. The black line is a guide for the eyes.

The vector \mathbf{n} is parameterized by the standard spherical angles: $\mathbf{n} = \sin \vartheta \cos \varphi \cdot \hat{e}_1 + \sin \vartheta \sin \varphi \cdot \hat{e}_2 + \cos \vartheta \cdot \hat{e}_3$. Note that in general the ‘internal’ axes \hat{e}_i may not coincide with the crystallographic directions, but in the case of a strong easy-plane anisotropy we assume that $\hat{e}_3 \equiv \hat{x}$.

The Zeeman energy of the spins in the external magnetic field along \hat{x} gives: $H_Z = - \int (dx/a) \mu_0 H \cdot \mu_B S \cdot \cos \vartheta$, μ_B is the Bohr magneton, $\mu_0 H$ is the magnetic field, and we further denote $h = \mu_B \mu_0 H$.

Let us briefly discuss the doubly degenerate ground state of the system, which allows for the formation of domain walls. In the easy plane, $\vartheta = \pi/2$, the Hamiltonian takes the simplest form:

$$H[\varphi] = \frac{JS^2 a^2}{2} \int \frac{dx}{a} \left\{ -\frac{\tilde{\theta}^2}{2} (\partial_x \varphi)^2 + \frac{a^2}{4} [(\partial_x \varphi)^4 + (\partial_x^2 \varphi)^2] \right\}. \quad (4)$$

Variational equation with respect to $\varphi(x)$,

$$2(\tilde{\theta}^2/a^2) \partial_x^2 \varphi - 6(\partial_x \varphi)^2 \partial_x^2 \varphi + \partial_x^4 \varphi = 0, \quad (5)$$

admits the solution $\varphi(x) = q \cdot x$ with an arbitrary q , corresponding to the homogeneous rotation of magnetic moments in space. The ground state can be found by substituting the solution into the Hamiltonian (4) and minimizing the energy with respect to the pitch wavenumber q , which gives two degenerate states with $q = \pm \tilde{\theta}/a$, ‘‘right-handed’’ (‘‘+’’) and ‘‘left-handed’’ (‘‘-’’) helicoids.

The excited state, an isolated chiral domain wall (DW) that connects two opposite chiralities, corresponds to another exact solution of Eq. (5) in the form $\varphi(x) = \text{Incosh}(q \cdot x)$ with $q = \tilde{\theta}/a$ (see Fig. 1). This analytical profile will be used in the collective coordinates approach (Sec. V) under the assumption that the shape of a DW does not change during the motion.

The time dynamics of \mathbf{n} , as well as the adiabatic effect of an electric current (spin-transfer torque) along \hat{x} can be implemented via the vector potential of the Dirac monopole in the Lagrangian (see, e.g., [9]):

$$L = \int \frac{dx}{a} \left\{ -\hbar S (\mathbf{A} \cdot \partial_t \mathbf{n}) - j^{(s)} a^3 (\mathbf{A} \cdot \partial_x \mathbf{n}) \right\} - H - H_Z. \quad (6)$$

here $j^{(s)} = j^{(c)} \cdot P \hbar / (2e)$, with $j^{(c)}$ being the density of an electric current, P – its spin polarization, e is the elementary

charge, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant. The vector potential has the form $\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{n}_0 \times \mathbf{n}] / (1 + \mathbf{n}_0 \cdot \mathbf{n})$, where \mathbf{n}_0 can be chosen arbitrarily, $\mathbf{n}_0 = \hat{x}$ in what follows.

The term $\mathbf{A} \cdot \partial_x \mathbf{n}$ can be expanded as $(1 - \cos \vartheta) \cdot \partial_x \varphi$. The $-\cos \vartheta \cdot \partial_x \varphi$ part reproduces the spin-transfer torque in the dynamical equations. However, the term $\partial_x \varphi$ makes the right- and left-handed rotations inequivalent by the presence of current only. In recent experiments [5, 6] it was shown that a magnetic field is necessary to lift the chirality degeneracy. Thus, in Sec. IV and V we first analyze the corresponding effects without this ‘‘gauge’’ term, which comes from the unity in brackets, and comment on its possible influence at the end of those sections.

Finally, we work in a limit of small magnetic fields and currents and treat the out-of-plane angle $\vartheta(x, t)$ as a ‘‘slave’’ field, which will be proportional to the gradients of $\varphi(x, t)$, as well as to the magnetic field. It allows us to consider only linear and quadratic corrections to the Lagrangian and neglect relatively small cubic and quartic terms (e.g., $(\partial_x \varphi)^3$, $(\partial_x \varphi)^4$), which come from field or/and current.

Let us look at the intermediate Lagrangian to integrate out the ‘‘massive’’ $\cos \vartheta$ -field (large anisotropy limit):

$$L = \int \frac{dx}{a} \left\{ (1 - \cos \vartheta) [\hbar S \partial_t \varphi + j^{(s)} a^3 \partial_x \varphi] \right\} - H - H_Z. \quad (7)$$

$$H = S^2 \int \frac{dx}{a} \left\{ \frac{J a^2}{2} \left[-\frac{\tilde{\theta}^2}{2} (\partial_x \varphi)^2 + \frac{a^2}{4} (\partial_x \varphi)^4 + \frac{a^2}{4} (\partial_x^2 \varphi)^2 \right] \sin^2 \vartheta + K \cos^2 \vartheta \right\}. \quad (8)$$

The Euler-Lagrange equation $\delta L / \delta (\cos \vartheta) = 0$ with $K \gg J \cdot \tilde{\theta}^4$ gives

$$\cos \vartheta = [\hbar (\partial_t \varphi + v \cdot \partial_x \varphi) + h] / 2KS, \quad (9)$$

where we denoted $v = j^{(s)} a^3 / (\hbar S)$, the ‘‘spin-transfer velocity’’ [10].

The relation (9) allows us to solve the effective Lagrangian for the angle $\varphi(x, t)$. In the above mentioned approximation, the Lagrangian (7) takes the form:

$$L = \int \frac{dx}{a} \left\{ \hbar S (\dot{\varphi} + v \varphi') + \frac{\hbar^2}{4K} (\dot{\varphi} + v \varphi')^2 - \frac{JS^2 a^2}{2} \left[\frac{a^2}{4} (\varphi'^4 + \varphi''^2) - \frac{\tilde{\theta}^2}{2} \varphi'^2 \right] + \frac{h}{2KS} \cdot \hbar S (\dot{\varphi} + v \varphi') \right\}. \quad (10)$$

$\dot{\varphi}$ and φ' are time and space derivatives of φ , respectively, and we also highlight $h/(2KS) \equiv h/h_c = \tilde{h}$.

In a similar manner, we write down the continuous Rayleigh dissipation function:

$$R = \int \frac{dx}{a} \left\{ \frac{\hbar S \alpha_G}{2} (\partial_t \mathbf{n})^2 + \beta j^{(s)} a^3 (\partial_t \mathbf{n} \cdot \partial_x \mathbf{n}) \right\}, \quad (11)$$

or

$$R = \int (dx/a) \left\{ \hbar S \alpha_G \cdot \dot{\varphi}^2 / 2 + \beta j^{(s)} a^3 \cdot \dot{\varphi} \varphi' \right\}, \quad (12)$$

α_G is the Gilbert damping constant, β is the coefficient of non-adiabaticity of the spin-transfer torque.

III. SPIN-TRANSFER TORQUE EFFECTS ON A SINGLE HELIX

A. Non-adiabatic torque: homogeneous rotation

We start the analysis of the motion of a helimagnetic system under the action of current by considering a single domain state with a certain chirality, which the system consists of for the most part, and any inhomogeneities, such as domain walls and other defects, are assumed to be driven along with the continuous rotation of the phase. Such a motion is effectively governed by the dissipative terms, and the corresponding equation of motion reduces to

$$\dot{\varphi} \approx -(\beta/\alpha_G) v \cdot \varphi' \quad (13)$$

for the homogeneous rotation of a helix. $\varphi = q(x - V \cdot t)$ is the simplest solution to Eq. (13), which corresponds to the translational shift of the magnetic profile along the positive \hat{x} direction with velocity $V = (\beta/\alpha_G) \cdot v$. For a single-domain state it is indistinguishable from a homogeneous rotation with angular velocity $\omega = -qV$. For example, if the right-handed helix profile, $\varphi = qx$, $q > 0$, is “translated” to the right, the angle φ decreases at each point x , which corresponds to negative angular velocity ($\omega < 0$).

This type of motion has also recently been demonstrated in micromagnetic simulations for a helicoid stabilized by the Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction [11]. It is a general feature of the action of a non-adiabatic torque in such systems, present due to the constant spatial gradient of magnetic moments. This so called sliding motion, induced by current, was investigated experimentally in the helimagnetic MnAu₂ [12].

B. Adiabatic torque: out-of-plane tilt

As follows from Eqs. (9) and (13), for $\varphi = q(x - V \cdot t)$ in the absence of a magnetic field:

$$\cos \vartheta = \frac{\hbar q}{2KS} v \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{\alpha_G} \right). \quad (14)$$

The induced out-of-plane angle is proportional to the current density v , the helical wavenumber q , and the ratio $1 - (\beta/\alpha_G)$.

This indicates that opposite chiralities have different cantings under the action of a current. While chiral domains being originally degenerate, the magnetic field, along with the current-induced tilt, causes the energy difference between the right and left chirality, leading to the chirality switching mechanism, demonstrated in a number of recent works [5–7].

As was pointed out in micromagnetic simulations of helimagnetic MnP in [7] and explained by energy dissipation considerations, the choice of chirality in the field decreasing process is inverted when $\beta > \alpha_G$, which is consistent with (14).

This tilting is accompanied by a finite twist of the in-plane angle φ . Varying the first term of the Lagrangian (7) with respect to φ (all other terms do not contribute to the rotational dynamics under the assumption of homogeneity of ϑ and for a uniform helix state) and accounting for the dissipation with the Rayleigh function in a form $R = \int (dx/a) \{ \hbar S \alpha_G \cdot \dot{\varphi}^2 \cdot \sin^2 \vartheta / 2 \}$ we obtain:

$$\sin^2 \vartheta \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\alpha_G} \frac{\partial (\cos \vartheta)}{\partial t}, \quad (15)$$

which integrates to $\Delta\varphi = (1/\alpha_G) \cdot \ln \tan(\vartheta_f/2)$ [13], where ϑ_f can be calculated using the relation (9) (recall that $\vartheta \approx \pi/2$). After turning off the current, the helix rotates by the same angle $\Delta\varphi$ in the opposite direction. This change of phase also occurs in the case of the application of a magnetic field along the helical axis \hat{x} .

To calculate the time scale of this rotation, we solve the dynamical equation corresponding to the Lagrangian (10) for a homogeneous helix ($\varphi' = q = \text{const}$), taking into account the time dependence of a current and neglecting the non-adiabaticity:

$$\ddot{\varphi} + (2\alpha_G KS/\hbar) \dot{\varphi} + q\dot{v}(t) = 0. \quad (16)$$

From this equation, one concludes that the angular acceleration is present during the saturation of a current from 0 to some value v . At a constant current, only the damping is present, the initially received momentum dissipates over the characteristic time period $T_\alpha = \hbar/(2\alpha_G KS)$, which lies on the picosecond scale. Further rotation requires the non-adiabatic force.

C. Renormalization of the helical pitch

We can analyze the quasi-stationary energy of a helix by writing the potential energy density of the Lagrangian (10) as a function of $\psi \equiv \partial_\xi \varphi$, $\xi = x/a$ in the presence of a current (the full-derivative terms are omitted to capture only the effects on equations of motion):

$$\tilde{U}(\psi) = \frac{1}{4} \psi^4 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\tilde{\theta}^2 + \frac{\hbar^2 v^2}{JKS^2 a^2} \right) \cdot \psi^2. \quad (17)$$

The obvious result of (17) is the renormalization of an equilibrium helical wavenumber $\tilde{q} = q \cdot a$ from $\pm\tilde{\theta}$ initially to $\pm\sqrt{\tilde{\theta}^2 + \hbar^2 v^2 / (JKS^2 a^2)}$. The preferable spatial rotation rate

FIG. 2. (a) The result of evolution of a $\varphi(\xi, \tau)$ -profile (in dimensionless variables, $\xi = x/a$) under the current $j^{(c)} = 3.7 \cdot 10^{12}$ A/m² ($P = 1$, $S = 1$) after the time interval $\Delta t = 100$ ns. $K = 50$ meV, $J = 10$ meV, $a = 0.5$ nm. Orange dashed line represents the initial state – single right handed helix with $\tilde{\theta} = 0.01$; blue curve – final state that consists of many domains with larger helical wavenumber (larger slope). (b) The spatial derivative of $\varphi(\xi, \tau)$. Initial state – orange line, final state – blue curve, black dashed lines correspond to new equilibrium values of the pitch wavenumber $\tilde{q} = \pm \sqrt{\tilde{\theta}^2 + \hbar^2 v^2 / (JKS^2 a^2)}$. The slope is fixed on the initial value at the boundaries, but the “bulk” dynamics is affected by the renormalization.

of magnetic moments increases when an electric current is present.

However, the continuous transition from the ground state to the new pitch is not trivial. The overall dynamics of φ is suppressed due to the easy-plane confinement. The numerical solution of the variational equations of the Lagrangian (10) shows that at sufficiently large currents, when the renormalized \tilde{q}_1 is a few times larger than $\tilde{q}_0 = \tilde{\theta}$ of the initial state, after 10-100 nanoseconds the uniform helix breaks into many domains with opposite chiralities with slope $a \cdot \varphi' \approx \tilde{q}_1 = \pm \sqrt{\tilde{\theta}^2 + \hbar^2 v^2 / (JKS^2 a^2)}$, separated by chiral domain walls (Fig. 2a, 2b).

IV. EFFECT OF FIELD AND CURRENT ON CHIRALITY POTENTIAL

The magnetic field, applied along \hat{x} , induces a finite out-of-plane angle, according to Eq. (9). The simultaneously applied electric current shifts $\cos \vartheta$ in opposite ways for different chiralities of the domains. The energy difference, which lifts the degeneracy, is incorporated in the $\hbar v \cdot \varphi'$ -term of the Lagrangian (10). Following Sec. III C, we write the potential energy, including the field effect:

$$\tilde{U}(\psi) = \frac{1}{4} \psi^4 - \frac{1}{2} \tilde{q}^2 \cdot \psi^2 - \tilde{f} \cdot \psi \quad (18)$$

with $\tilde{q}^2 = \tilde{\theta}^2 + \hbar^2 v^2 / (JKS^2 a^2)$ and $\tilde{f} = \hbar \cdot \hbar v / (JKS^2 a)$. Now, the potential wells become asymmetric for small currents and fields. For definiteness, we choose $v, h > 0$, the positive chirality becomes energetically preferable in the presence of both current and field. We analyze the behavior of the system by looking at the potential energy for different values of field and

current. Let us find the condition under which the left (more energetic) chirality well disappears completely. The extrema of $\tilde{U}'(\psi)$ are found from $\tilde{U}''(\psi_{\pm}) = 0$, $\psi_{\pm} = \pm \tilde{q} / \sqrt{3}$. We want the potential to be monotonic in the vicinity of the left well, which requires $\tilde{U}'(\psi_-) \leq 0$, or

$$\left(\tilde{\theta}^2 + \frac{\hbar^2 v^2}{JKS^2 a^2} \right)^{3/2} \leq \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2} \cdot \frac{\hbar v}{JKS^2 a}. \quad (19)$$

This inequality can be analyzed graphically by plotting both sides of (19) with respect to the current $v \sim j^{(c)}$ for different values of h . The left hand side is the parabola, shifted vertically; the right hand side is the line passing through the point (0,0), its slope is defined by h (Fig. 3).

The minimum value of the field necessary to make a potential well unstable is $h_{\min} = S\sqrt{JK} \cdot \tilde{\theta}^2$, and the value of the critical current (at the tangent point) is $v_{\min} = \sqrt{JK/2} \cdot \tilde{\theta} Sa / \hbar$. Further increase of the magnetic field $h > h_{\min}$ extends the interval of current values around v_{\min} at which the instability occurs. At larger currents $v \gg v_{\min}$, the effect of renormalization, discussed in the previous section, dominates the linear shift, and the left well appears again.

From (10), one concludes that the “gauge” effect can be incorporated via the substitution $h \mapsto h + 2KS$. Now, even at $h = 0$ the wells become asymmetric and, as long as the condition $J\tilde{\theta}^4 \ll 4K$ is satisfied (which was also previously assumed in (9)), the current value required to eliminate the left potential well always exists.

V. CHIRAL DOMAIN WALL DYNAMICS

First, we should rewrite the description of the system in dimensionless coordinates $\xi = x/a$ and $\tau = t \cdot c/a$ with $c =$

FIG. 3. Graphical solution of inequality (19). Blue curve corresponds to the left-hand side of (19); black dashed lines correspond to different values of magnetic field on the right-hand side. $h = \{3.0 \cdot 10^{-5}, 7.0 \cdot 10^{-5}, 13.0 \cdot 10^{-5}\} \cdot h_c$ respectively, where the critical field $h_c = 2KS$ (see eq. (9)). The yellow filled region represents the parameters' $(j^{(c)}, h)$ values, at which only one chirality remains stable, $\tilde{\theta} = 0.01$.

$a\sqrt{2JK}/\hbar$, and denote the dimensionless parameter of the current, $\tilde{v} = v/c$. The Lagrangian (10) and the Rayleigh function (12) take the following form:

$$L = J \int d\xi \left\{ \frac{1}{2}(\dot{\varphi} + \tilde{v}\varphi')^2 - \frac{S^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{4}(\varphi'^4 + \varphi''^2) - \frac{\tilde{\theta}^2}{2}\varphi'^2 \right] + S\sqrt{\frac{2K}{J}}(\dot{\varphi} + \tilde{v}\varphi') \left[1 + \frac{h}{2KS} \right] \right\}, \quad (20)$$

$$\tilde{R} = J \int d\xi S\sqrt{\frac{2K}{J}} \left\{ \frac{\alpha_G}{2}\varphi^2 + \beta\tilde{v}\dot{\varphi}\varphi' \right\},$$

such that $\delta L/\delta\varphi = \partial\tilde{R}/\partial\dot{\varphi}$, and all derivatives are now with respect to the new variables.

To describe the motion of a chiral domain wall, connecting domains with left and right chiralities in a quasi-one-dimensional nanostructure (nanowire, nanostripe, etc.), we use the collective coordinates approach and insert the ansatz of a rigid DW into the Lagrangian and Rayleigh function in a following form: $\varphi(\xi, \tau) = \text{Incosh}[\tilde{\theta}(\xi - \xi_{DW}(\tau))]$, where ξ_{DW} is the center of a DW. It represents the translation of a DW profile along the \hat{x} -axis.

To incorporate the effect of the full derivative, φ' -term in the Lagrangian (20), we consider a large but finite system with the longitudinal size $l_x = N_x \cdot a$, where $N_x \gg 1$ is a number of spins in the direction of the helical axis \hat{x} . Let us note on this term. Its integral over the length of the system is calculated as

follows:

$$\int_{-N_x/2}^{N_x/2} \varphi' d\xi \approx \tilde{\theta} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tanh[\tilde{\theta}(\xi - \xi_{DW}(\tau))] d\xi = -2\xi_{DW}(\tau). \quad (21)$$

One can see that it acts as a force on the generalized “quasiparticle-like” DW profile, allowing for the constant-velocity solution in the presence of damping.

The terms, which contain even powers of $\tanh[\tilde{\theta}(\xi - \xi_{DW}(\tau))]$, are proportional to the finite length of the system after the integration (e.g., φ^2 , $\varphi\varphi'$ in both the Lagrangian and the dissipative function). The exchange energy part remains constant, as the form of the soliton is assumed to remain unperturbed during the motion. The Lagrangian and the Rayleigh function in collective coordinates (without the “gauge” term) read

$$L_{\text{eff}} = \frac{1}{2}N_x\tilde{\theta}^2\xi_{DW}^2 - \frac{2\tilde{\theta}h\tilde{v}}{\sqrt{2JK}}\xi_{DW}, \quad (22)$$

$$\tilde{R}_{\text{eff}} = N_xS\tilde{\theta}^2\sqrt{\frac{2K}{J}} \left\{ \frac{\alpha_G}{2}\xi_{DW}^2 - \beta\tilde{v}\xi_{DW} \right\}.$$

The equation of motion for ξ_{DW} has the solution $\dot{\xi}_{DW} = \tilde{V}_{DW} = \text{const}$:

$$\tilde{V}_{DW} = \frac{\beta}{\alpha_G}\tilde{v} - \frac{h\tilde{v}}{\alpha_GN_x\tilde{\theta} \cdot KS}. \quad (23)$$

The first term is simply the non-adiabatic contribution that has a direct continuous analog (13), found previously in Sec. III A, thus, the whole domain wall profile moves along with the phase, as expected, if the spatial deformations can be neglected. The second term, however, does not appear in the dynamical equation for φ , though, it comes from the Zeeman energy and affects the magnetization along \hat{x} . It effectively describes the energy difference between two chiral domains, which are connected by the domain wall in the presence of field and current. The motion under this term can be interpreted as sustained by the gain in energy, when the unfavorable domain is being expelled from the system during the continuous movement of a domain wall center, and the low-energy one expands.

From the physical perspective, the (quasi-static) part of magnetization along \hat{x} , which is induced by current, is proportional to $\tilde{v} \cdot \partial_x \varphi$, see Eq. (9). The magnetization profile forms an Ising type domain wall above the chiral DW, with zero magnetization at the center, where the rotation of spins stops. The magnetic field along the \hat{x} -axis tries to expand the domain with the aligned magnetization projection, but its action is localized in the vicinity of a DW, while the continuous motion of a magnetic profile requires the phase shift along the whole system (dynamics is confined in an easy-plane), which explains the $1/N_x$ factor in this force term.

To estimate the significance of this effect, we compare both velocities with respect to the length of the system N_x . The second term becomes larger than the “non-adiabatic” velocity under the condition:

$$N_x \leq \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{2\hbar}{\tilde{\theta}}, \quad (24)$$

where $0 \leq \tilde{h} \ll 1$.

Finally, substitution $h \mapsto h + 2KS$ into (23) simply magnifies the "adiabatic" part of the DW velocity.

VI. NUMERICAL ESTIMATES

First of all, we should check the validity of the approximation by evaluating the out-of-plane angle by means of Eq. (9). We take the value of the uniaxial anisotropy constant K typical for rare earth elements [14]: $K_2 \sim 5 \cdot 10^7$ J/m³, which corresponds to $K = 40$ meV for the unit cell volume a^3 with $a = 0.5$ nm. Now, at $j^{(c)} = 10^{12}$ A/m², $\cos \vartheta \approx 0.003$. Here and further $\tilde{\theta} = 0.5$ and $J \sim 10$ meV (roughly ~ 120 K in temperature units) [15]. The magnetic field of magnitude ≈ 1 T induces the angle with $\cos \vartheta = 0.0007$. We conclude that the easy-plane limit is maintained.

However, such anisotropy values may be too large, preventing the possibility of chirality switching by the mechanism described in Sec. IV. $h_{\min} \sim \sqrt{JK}$, which corresponds to the magnetic field $B_{\min} = \mu_0 H_{\min} \sim 250$ T and to the switching current $j_{\min}^{(c)} \sim 10^{13}$ A/m² for the finite helimagnetic angle $\tilde{\theta}$ ($\approx 30^\circ$), at least at zero temperature.

The velocity of a domain wall, caused by the non-adiabatic spin-transfer torque for $\beta \approx \alpha_G$, $P = 1$, $S = 1$:

$$V[\text{m/s}] \approx 4.0 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot j^{(c)}[\text{A/m}^2], \quad (25)$$

where $j^{(c)}$ is the density of the electric current. Therefore, for currents up to $\sim 10^{12}$ A/m² the chiral DW can potentially reach the velocity ~ 400 m/s.

Finally, to analyze the inequality (24), we take $\beta \approx 0.01$, and $\tilde{h} = 0.5$, which gives $N_x \leq 200$ spins (~ 30 helical periods) or ≈ 100 nm. Thus, the effect of the field on the velocity of a DW (23) requires sufficiently large magnetic fields to be observed, even in nanostructures.

VII. CONCLUSION

We have investigated the dynamics of the internal degree of freedom - chirality - and the motion of chiral domain walls in magnets with frustrated interaction under the action of an electric current and a magnetic field. The adiabatic effects of current induce the magnetization along the local rotational axis, which is responsible for the chirality switching and for the additional term in the domain wall velocity when acting together with the magnetic field. The non-adiabatic part contributes to the movement of topological defects along with the phase in the easy-plane picture, which allows for the purely electrical switching, avoiding the effects of the magnetic field, suppressed by the strong anisotropy.

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